

3D-Cipher – 3D-CT digitalisation of historical cipher machines

Introduction

As part of the 3D-Cipher project (2020-2023), funded by the German Feder Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF)¹, the Deutsches Museum together with the Fraunhofer EZRT/ISS² conducted computed tomography scans of 60 cipher machines from their cryptography collection. This form of digitalisation makes it possible to explore the encryption technologies hidden inside without irreparable damage to the historical exhibits.

The CT datasets are now available as Open Data for researches and the general public.

The scans of all cipher devices are provided in the established DICOM (.dcm) format and can be viewed using any CT-Viewer that supports the DICOM standard to generate 2D-CD and 3D-CD imaging. Some datasets contain subsets of the cipher machine in form of ROIs or segmentations, i.e. extracted mechanical parts of the machines. If available, these ROIs will also be provided in the DICOM format and for VGStudio users in the proprietary .xvgr format to import in VGStudio.

Additionally all CT scans of the cipher machines are integrated in a Web CT-Viewer – developed by the Fraunhofer EZRT/IIS – for real-time viewing and inspection on the Website of the Deutsches Museum.³ The CT datasets are also uploaded on the MorphoSource repository.⁴

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3D-CT-Image of cipher machine Kryptograph, Inv.-Nr.: 46453

¹ https://www.bmbf.de/bmbf/en/home/home_node.html (all links last accessed: 04.07.2023)

² <https://www.iis.fraunhofer.de/en/ff/zfp.html>

³ <https://ctview.dmd.zone/ct-viewer>

⁴ <https://www.morphosource.org/projects/000474834?locale=en>

Technology

CT scanner

To realise the technically complex project, the Deutsches Museum is collaborating with the Development Center X-ray Technology EZRT at the Fraunhofer Institute for Integrated Circuits IIS. Depending on the size and material density of the ciphering devices, different computed tomography equipment is used. Due to the penetrating properties of X-rays, the ciphering devices can be scanned together with their (wooden) cassings and the wrapping required for transport.

The largest cipher units are scanned in the XXL-CT facility, that was already used for the CT scan of the Messerschmitt Me163.

XXL-CT facility of Fraunhofer IIS. Image: Deutsches Museum | Sebastian Linstädt

Resolution

The spatial resolution ranges between 0.7 and 0.1 mm, at the technical limit for objects with a high metal percentage of this size. The quality difference is obvious in direct comparison, as seen from the cross sections of a keyboard key

... from a Lorenz SZ 42 (resolution: 0.67 mm)...

.... and from an Enigma I (resolution: 0.18 mm)

2D-CT-Images

The scanning process produces hundreds to thousands of X-ray images, which enable a digital reconstruction of the objects. Unlike classic X-ray images, the 2D sectional images from CT scanning can be displayed with voxel accuracy (voxel= pixel in 3D space) at any position and angle without other 2D layers in front or behind. Thanks to digital tools, various measurements (length, angle, porosity, etc.) can be made.

2D-CT cross section of a Hagelin CD-57, Inv.-Nr.: 2018-389

3D-CT-Images

CT processing programmes calculate and render 3D volumes from the reconstructed X-ray images. Grey values are assigned to the different materials by the scanning process, which allows the user to fade different materials in or out. Extensive modification of CT data is possible with regard to opacity, colourfulness, position etc.

3D-CT-Image of TST 970 with semi-transparent casing, Inv.-Nr.: 2017-426

3D-CT-Image, cut with colorized and segmented parts from a Schlüsselgerät 41, Image: © Fraunhofer IIS

Why CT?

CT images provide impressions of the inner workings of the mysterious cipher devices and serve as the basis for extensive analyses. This makes the use of the technology interesting for both research and museum educational purposes. Some examples of use cases are listed below.

Insights

CT technology provides insights into the cipher units. Comprehensive analyses and visualisations that would not be possible with other 2D and 3D image acquisition methods can be realised using computed tomography. E.g. the mechanics and the closed casings of cipher devices can be viewed side by side and superimposed.

Hagelin M-209, Inv.-Nr.: 2019-397

The M-209 was developed by Boris Hagelin at the beginning of the Second World War. The purely mechanical cipher machine was small, handy and had an integrated printer. It was used by the US Army and is probably the most produced cipher machine worldwide.

Nominal-Actual Comparison

With the help of CT images, different units of the same type can easily be compared. Deviations, structural changes or changes over time become visible and allow further analyses.

In the following, two versions of the Kryha Standard machine are compared on the basis of their CT data and their structural differences are made clear.

On the basis of a digital section of the casing, similarities and differences between the models can be clearly identified. For example, the disc on the right of the newer unit is fixed with significantly more screws. Moreover, additional mechanical changes have been made in the front part.

Inv.-Nr.: 62797 (~1926)

Inv.-Nr.: 2017-384 (~1952)

Deviations can be colour-coded and visualised by mapping/overlaying CT data sets.

The structural changes in the front part are striking. The deviations at the top of the (rotatable) cipher discs of the two units are due to the different positions of the discs and do not indicate structural differences.

Colour-coded Nominal-Actual Comparison

Constructional Details

Thanks to the 2D images that can be viewed frame by frame, sub-millimetre details can be recognised as well as digitally measured.

E.g. the mechanical safety mechanism in the pocket-sized HC-520 unit is clearly visible in the 2D-CT-images. To change the battery and open the device, a screw that is in contact with a "tamper switch" must be loosened. If this connection is broken, the internal crypto-memory is erased.

Electronical cipher device Hagelin HC-520, Inv.-Nr.: 2017-406

Surface models

Surface models (surface meshes) can be created based on CT data. Due to the ability of X-ray and CT technology to penetrate materials, the surface must first be defined. In the case of an Enigma machine scanned in a wooden casing, either the wooden box, the casing of the Enigma or individual components can be determined as the "relevant surface". The results differ accordingly in the generated 3D surface model.

This surface determination defines significantly the quality of the generated polygon mesh. The determination becomes more complex, more difficult and more error-prone the more similar the materials of the surface and the surrounding areas are. Inaccuracies in the surface determination are directly visible in the mesh. With complex technical machines and machines consisting of several (similar) materials, this is a greater problem than, for example, with technically less complex objects.

Mesh of an Enigma M4 rotor, Inv.-Nr.: 2017-398

Segmentation

The supreme discipline of CT post-processing is the segmentation of individual components from a CT scan. Technically, this process is closely linked to the surface determination - thus, a segmentation can easily be made from a good surface determination. The segmentation of individual parts, especially the separation of identical materials, also offers the possibility of conveying complex mechanisms in a comprehensible way through visualisations and simple animations.

Analogous to surface determination, different materials can be segmented more easily than similar or even identical materials. For example, segmenting a wooden crank from a metal strut takes little effort, while separating individual, interlocking gears from each other takes a lot of time and effort.

Segmented components. Engima M4, Inv.-Nr.: 2017-398

Visualisation

3D-Viewer

Based on the CT data surface models can be generated, which in turn can be used as a basis for many other applications. 3D viewers invite users to explore the objects in a low-threshold and playful way and can help explain complex issues via annotations or through embedding in digital stories. Further use in AR or XR applications or gaming experiences is the next logical step, although it requires further development effort.

Bull BNE surface model on Sketchfab⁵

Kryptograph von Alexis Køhl on Sketchfab⁶

⁵ <https://skfb.ly/oDAqD>

⁶ <https://skfb.ly/oEzAT>

There are also CT-Web Viewers that are based on the Volume dataset in comparison to the surface models most 3D-Webviewers require. The obvious advantage is the possibility to inspect and manipulate the whole volume dataset, which include the interior regions and not only the surfaces. The drawback are much bigger files that need to be transferred and loaded by the user.

Hagelin CX-52 OTP via the CT-Webviewer by Fraunhofer EZRT/ISS⁷

Enigma M4 via the CT-Webviewer from MorphoSource⁸

⁷ <https://ctview.dmd.zone/ct-viewer>

⁸ <http://n2t.net/ark:/87602/m4/508415>

Animations

The 3D Cipher project wants to focus not only on research questions but also on the visualisation of CT data. Besides screenshots, videos are the simplest and most accessible form of visualisation. Due to the manipulability of the CT data in terms of colour scheme, segmented components and camera positions, a variety of display options are possible.⁹

Colorization

The colouring of the CT datasets is arbitrary and can be manipulated at will, since the acquisition with X-rays only produces grey values depending on the material. Materials with very low density (i.e. paper) are only detected very poorly or not at all by CT measurements. Therefore the letter plates on Charles Wheatstone's cipher disc could not be detected.

Image: Deutsches Museum | Konrad Rainer

3D-CT-Visualisation

⁹ A couple of examples can be found on Youtube for the Kryptograph by Alexis Køhl (<https://youtu.be/altjsgVooq4>), Hagelin M-209 (<https://youtu.be/QCj69uEQfDk>) and a swiss NEMA machine (<https://youtu.be/FCbzTbclfBw>)